

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

DISEASE RESISTANCE

Evaluation of National Uniform Rice Yield Trial 1985 against bacterial blight (BB) in Pakistan

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BB incited by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* (Ishiyama) Dye occurs in almost all provinces of Pakistan; it has caused considerable yield loss over the last 4 yr. We tested 19 rice cultivars for reaction to BB at 10 sites in different ecological zones under natural epiphytotic conditions in 1985.

Lines were planted in 4-m² plots at 20- × 15-cm spacing in a randomized block design with 4 replications.

Recommended agronomic practices were applied. Disease was measured according to the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES) 20 d before harvest.

Lateefy and IR161-1-1-1 showed the highest mean disease score, DM16-5-1 the lowest (see table). □

Response of rice cultivars to BB in Pakistan.

Cultivar	Score ^a	
Lateefy	6.20	h
IR161-1-1-1	6.20	h
DR83	5.80	gh
Swat II	5.80	gh
Swat I	5.40	fgh
Basmati 370-1	4.80	efgh
RGP135	4.80	efgh
DR82	4.60	defgh
KS282	3.80	cdefg
IR6	3.40	cdef
IR42	3.40	bcde
IR16461	3.20	bcde
IR8-5	2.60	abcd
IR2153-276	2.60	abcd
IR1529-ECIA	2.60	abcd
IR6-104	1.80	abc
Jajai 77-1	1.20	ab
Basmati 370	1.20	ab
DM16-5-1	1.00	a

^aBased on 1980 SES scale. 0-9: 0 = no incidence, 9 = 26-50% incidence. Each score is the average of 10 locations in different ecological zones of Pakistan. Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 1% level by Duncan's multiple range test.

Resistance of rice germplasm to bacterial blight (BB) at Ludhiana, India

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We evaluated a germplasm collection of rices obtained from various places in India and internationally for resistance to BB caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*. Each cultivar or line was planted in a 3-m row; standard agronomic practices were followed. At 70 d after sowing (DAS), each line was inoculated with isolate IXO-3, the most virulent of 11 isolates identified from the Punjab, using the standard clipping method. The inoculum consisted of 48-h-old growth of the bacterium, multiplied on PSA at 25 °C, at a

Mean lesion length and reaction of rice lines and cultivars to BB caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*. Ludhiana, India.

Cultivar or line name	Mean lesion length (cm)	
	70 DAS	90 DAS
<i>R at 70 DAS and 90 DAS</i>		
Palman 579	1.9	2.6
NCS83	0.4	1.4
NCS84	0.4	1.6
TCA368	1.0	2.6
IR22	1.6	1.0
DZ78	1.8	1.8
IR46828-B	1.6	2.6
IR18350-93-2	1.6	2.6
IR21820-154-3-2-2-3	1.9	3.0
IR25587-133-3-2-2-2	1.0	1.6
IR25916-42-3-3-2-2	1.6	1.6
IR27325-63-2-2	1.6	1.6
IR29692-65-2-3	1.6	3.0
IR31803-32-2	1.9	3.0
IR42	1.6	3.0
IR46	1.6	3.0
IR4744-295-2-3	1.0	3.4
IR50	1.6	1.6
CR333-6-1 (Jagannath/Mahsuri)	1.6	3.0
B4032D-MR-1-3-1	1.0	1.6
IR15529-253-3-2-2-2	1.6	2.6
IR15529-256-1	1.0	2.6
IR15795-151-2-3-2-2	1.0	1.6
IR15797-74-1-3-2	1.6	1.6
IR25586-108-1-2-2-2	1.9	3.4

Table continued.

Cultivar or line name	Mean lesion length (cm)	
	70 DAS	90 DAS
IR27316-6-2-2	1.9	3.0
IR28154-101-3-2	1.6	3.4
IR2035-117-3	1.6	3.0
IR64	1.6	3.0
<i>R at 70 DAS and MR at 90 DAS</i>		
Amritsari HR 22	1.9	5.6
ARC5752	1.6	5.6
NCS16	1.6	4.4
ARC10486	1.9	5.6
TCA728	1.4	4.0
201-1-27	1.9	5.0
PR107	1.4	4.0
RP2068-32-2-3	1.9	5.0
RP1801-21-24-20-9	1.9	4.4
IR13475-7-3-2	1.6	4.4
HAU2-165-3-3	1.6	3.8
IR13525-43-2-3-1-3-2	1.6	4.0
IR15529-256-1	1.9	4.2
IR19728-9-3-2	1.9	6.8
IR25587-67-1-3-3-3	1.6	6.4
IR48	1.9	5.4
NCS211	1.6	5.0
CR333-6-2 (Jagannath/Mahsuri)	1.6	5.0
IR15527-21-2-3	1.6	5.0
IR18350-93-2	1.9	5.0
HKR26	1.6	5.0
HKR36	1.6	6.4
<i>MR at 70 DAS and R at 90 DAS</i>		
Nagkayat (HB62)	3.2	3.4
Nagra 41/14	2.2	2.6
IR46830	(B)2.8	2.8
CR333-1-1-3 (Jagannath/Mahsuri)	4.0	6.2
CR333-1-15-2 (Jagannath/Mahsuri)	3.0	3.4
RP1800-14-11-22-4	2.6	3.0
IR13240-82-2-3-2-3-1	3.4	2.0
IR13538-48-2-3-1	2.4	3.0
IR15429-268-1-2-1	3.0	3.4
IR17492-18-6-1-1-3-3	3.6	2.6
IR25588-7-3-1	3.6	2.2
IR25863-35-3-3	3.0	3.4
IR28125-79-3-3-2	2.4	3.0
IR28154-101-3-2	3.0	3.0
IR54	3.0	3.6
IR56	2.6	3.0
IR58	3.0	3.0
Bahbolon	3.2	2.4
IR17492-18-6-1-1-3-3	3.0	1.0
IR21820-154-3-2-2-3	2.6	3.0
IR25587-133-3-2-2-2	3.2	1.0
IR27325-27-3-3	3.4	3.0
IR29692-65-2-3	3.0	1.6
IR31803-32-2	2.6	1.0
IR32307-107-3-2-2	3.0	1.6
HKR30	2.6	1.6
IR13475-7-3-2	3.8	3.0
IR13458-117-2-3-2-3	2.4	3.0
Susceptible check TN1	7.6	14.6